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Research Article

**PREVALENCE, EFFECTS AND CAUSES OF NECK PAIN AND
TREATMENT OF NECK PAIN BY THE USE OF THORACIC
MANUAL THERAPY**¹Dr. Ghulam Hadi Sarki, ²Dr. Zunaira Mazhar, ³Dr. Syeda Tanzeela Bukhari¹Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, Jamshoro /Hyderabad, ²Frontier Medical College Abbottabad, ³Shaheed Mohtarma Benazir Bhutto Medical University Larkana.**Article Received:** November 2020 **Accepted:** December 2020 **Published:** January 2021**Abstract:**

Background: Implausible human anguishes and monetary expenses are related with the neck soreness. Many corporeal therapies and non-persistent interferences can be utilized in the treatment of the neck soreness.

Methodology

For the treatment of neck soreness, the therapy which has been most commonly used is manual therapy. Use of cervical manual therapy possesses many risk factors to the patients.

Results

So it has been suggested that cervical manual therapy should be replaced by thoracic manual therapy to lessen the risk factors and achieve the objectives of treatment of neck pain.

Conclusion

The exact working principle of this therapy to treat the neck soreness is not well known. The goal of this article is to evaluate the current prose about the treatment of neck pain by using the thoracic manual therapy.

Keyword: Cervical, Manual therapy, Neck pain, Thoracic

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INTRODUCTION:

The 4th most essential disease related to muscles and skeleton that causes the disability in individuals is neck pain. [1] Throughout the world there are almost 300 million individuals exist that suffers from any kind of neck soreness. [2] 1.3 percent costs occur on the treatment of neck pain out of total cost spent on the health problems. On international scale, 5.8-38.6% neck soreness occurs in patients. [3]

Many management therapies and different cure are available to treat the neck pain. There are many persistent and non-persistent treatments present that are used for the management of neck soreness. [4] Pharmacological managements and corporeal therapies are the most common non-persistent treatment methods for the treatment of neck pain. Reprieve from neck soreness can also be achieved by the use of drugs but it is temporary solution. But long term and permanent relief can be obtained by the treatment with physical therapies. David et al observed and said that for the treatment of neck soreness corporeal therapy is the bastion. [6] The methods that have been most commonly chosen are discharge of myofascial, inactive broadening, and recruitment of tissues present in nerves and techniques of cervical recruitment. Some other methods like cervical toehold, waterless spinning, warm packs, muscle energy processes and ultrasound can also be used for the management of neck pain. [7]

MATERIAL AND METHODS:**Use of cervical manual therapy for the treatment of neck pain:**

Process of manual therapy has been found effective in the treatment of neck soreness. It has been stated by Hurley that 37.3% physicians treating the neck pain use the manual therapy for treatment. There are various points of view that describe the effectiveness of manual therapy. In this regard the most commonly accepted point of view is of Lederman. Manual therapy produces various consequences like neurological and biochemical effects as stated by Lederman. Manual therapy produces the most common effect in the patient that is related to psychology. After manual therapy some psychological results like sentiment of happiness and leisure in body.

Treatment made by the use of cervical manual therapy produces optimistic results in most of the cases. However, some complex impediments can also be observed when the patients were not properly cared before the start of cervical manual therapy. The complications were mostly observed in the patients

having chances of vertebrobasilar insufficiency (VBI). If vertebrobasilar insufficiency is more complicated then it also causes the disorders of brain. It has been suggested by Haldeman and his companions that cervical manual therapy especially manipulation processes needs precautions for proper management of neck pain. These precautions are necessary to take because the devices and apparatus used for the treatment are not properly sanitized and excellent to treat the disorder. It has been stated by the Canadian therapists that the patients should undergo the screening examinations before the application of cervical manual therapy.

It has been shown by the measurements and calculations that risk factors are the most common observations seen by the therapists during the cervical manual therapy. Psychoanalysts need to apply physical forces inside restrictions of constancy to shun the solemn impediments during the treatment of neck pain. It has been observed by Mann and associated that to shun the risk factors of physical therapy the most essential distress is impartial cervical location because it is more imperative than amount of power used in the treatment of neck pain. It has been summarized that to lessen the risk factors of the cervical manual therapy tremendous varieties of cervical conservatory and revolution must be shunned.

Use of thoracic manual therapy for the treatment of neck pain:

As treating the neck pain by the cervical manual therapy offers many risk factors so it has been pointed out by Erhard and his companions that thoracic manual therapy should be used instead of cervical manual therapy to shun the risk factors. The main objective of the use of thoracic manual therapy is to accomplish the ambition that cannot be attained by cervical manual therapy.

Spines present in the neck areas that have some issues related to structure, neuronal and biochemical problems cause the soreness in neck. However there are very few confirmations that prove the treatment of neck pain by using the spines in the neck region. It has been said by the Cleland and associates that for the cure of neck pain cervical manual therapy is more helpful in treatment as compare to thoracic manual therapy. So he suggested using thoracic manual therapy for the treatment of the neck pain. But in the sufferers of neck pain having the issues of VBI we recommend to use thoracic manual therapy instead to cervical manual therapy. Thoracic manual therapy is useful in reducing the thoracic pain but the process how it works in the reduction of neck pain is not

known. It has been confirmed that a close anatomical and biochemical connection is present between the cervical and thoracic manual therapy. There is a close relationship exist between upper and lower thoracic vertebrae.

There is substantial connection exist between thoracic spine hypo mobility and thoracic pain because of connection between spines of thoracic and cervical. The neck pain commonly arises due to tension of muscles and allocation of irregular joint forces. This is caused by the maintenance of correct location of head by the connection of thoracic and cervical. The functions of muscles can be disorganized by the variations in curvatures of thoracic spinal that is also a biggest cause of neck pain. The standard position of thoracic spine can be relocated by the thoracic manual therapy. Thoracic manual therapy lessens the tension present on the cervical spines and normalizes the forces distributed on the joints. These are the causes we can say that thoracic manual therapy gives optimistic results in the treatment of neck pain. Stretched muscles can be normalizing by the mechanical responses produced by the thoracic manual therapy that helps in release of neck pain.

Although proves regarding the effectiveness of the thoracic manual therapy are not confirmed but still many therapeutics uses some techniques of manual therapy for the treatment of neck pain. It was stated by Hutchinson that most of the therapeutics uses thoracic manual therapy for the management of thoracic pain. It was argued by the Adams and Sim that in UK most of the doctor's uses the techniques of manual therapy for the treatment of neck pain in the thoracic area although they don't have confirmations about its effectiveness. But they use this procedure of treatment because it has very few side effects as compare to cervical manual therap. Some of the side effects caused by thoracic manual therapy are tenderness on thoracic region, sensation of tension in spinal area etc.

RESULTS:

A haphazard experiment was carried out by Cleland and associated. 36 sufferers were added into this study. These patients were chosen on random basis. To groups were formulated which are thoracic exploitation group and panacea group. The aim of this study was to assess the efficiency of thoracic spine exploitation in the soreness of neck. Reduction in the soreness of neck has been seen after the application of thoracic spine manipulation. This has been described in the consequences of the experiment carried out. The betterment found in patients present in thoracic manipulation group was estimated to be

15.6-7.6. However in placebo group the reduction in neck pain was found to be 4.2-4.5. There were no special adverse effects found in patients who have been treated by thoracic exploitation spines. The only one adverse effect observed was tenderness that was found to be present in the meeting point of thoracic and cervical region.

Another randomized trial was conducted by Gonzsalez-Iglesias and associated. The objective of this experiment was to analyze the efficiency of thoracic exploitation and use of substantial means in the reduction of neck pain. Patients suffering from neck pain were distributed into two groups. One was investigational group and the other was control group. Corporeal means were added into both groups. Corporeal means included TENS and burning packs. Investigational group was found to be more effective. Because the patients of investigational group reported reduction in their neck pain to greater extent as compare to control group. It has been resulted from the above experiment that use of corporeal means along with the thoracic exploitation spines is very effective in the reduction of soreness of neck in patients.

This observation were made by Lau and associated. In this experiment they assessed the efficiency of thoracic manipulation in neck soreness. Patients suffering from neck pain were divided into two groups. Thoracic exploitation in addition with physical workout and infrared waves were given to the patients in first group. While to the second group of patients they only treat them by giving physical workout and infrared waves. Thoracic manipulation was avoided in the patients of second group. The reduction in the soreness of the neck was seen in the patients of first group who received physical workout, radiations along with the implementation of thoracic exploitation spines. So we have concluded from this experiment that thoracic exploitation therapy along with radiations and physical workout is significant in the treatment of neck pain.

DISCUSSION:

32 patients of neck pain was separated by Kruss and associated. Two groups were formulated that were EG And CG . [8] Patients were added into these two groups. 22 patients were added in EG group and 210 patients were added in CG group. Thoracic manual therapy was applied on the patients of EG for the treatment of neck pain. [9] On the other hands patients of CG did not receive any intrusion. Face pain scales were used to measure the neck pain in patients of both groups. Cervical ROM was found to be elevated in EG patients. Its elevated level was

about 8.16. On the other hand ROM was declined in CG patients. The reduction of ROM was estimated to

about -0.5 in CG patients. [10]

TABLE 1: Literature present about the treatment of neck pain using thoracic manual therapy.

Author	Observational group	Manageable group	Follow up	Measurement of consequences	Results
Caleland and associated	Thoracic manual therapy	panacea	Thoracic manual therapy was followed instantly within 2 to 4 days	VAS	Reduction in neck pain was seen in the observational group
Gonzalez-Iglesias and associated	Electrotherapy in addition with thoracic manual therapy	Electrotherapy	7 days	NPRS NPQ	Observational group shows reduction in the pain of neck in Patients
Lau and associated	Physical workout, infrared waves and thoracic manual therapy	Infrared waves and physical workout	1 month 3 month Half year	NPRS NPQ	In observational group betterment in neck pain and disability was observed as compared to control group
Kruss and associated	Only thoracic manual therapy	No intrusion	Thoracic manual therapy was instantly followed	FPS	The sensation of pain in neck was found to significantly decrease in observational group as compare to control or manageable group

CONCLUSION:

For the management of neck pain manual therapy is most effective as found in writing. For the reduction of neck pain thoracic manual therapy was found to be useful in the examinations carried out in earlier times. However later on it was observed that literature for the use of thoracic manual therapy is not present. More searches are needed to avail the thoracic manual therapy as an effective treatment method for the management of neck pain in patients.

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